

SZ-HB-II-02-09 Taking a course at another university (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261343
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Title	Taking a course at another university
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Nadine - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951710
Short description	Nadine wants to take a course at another University. However, she doesn't know whether she can use the learning management systems of both universities together and take the course without any problems.
Result	Nadine can participate in the course and subsequently transfer a module certificate to her data wallet.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Register for a course at another university"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nadine is registered at BIRD• Nadine is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #workspace
Services / tools	#STUD-IP

Problem scenario

Introduction

Nadine Kasoevi is studying educational sciences and mathematics at the University of Vechta and is in her 8th semester. To get an overview for a possible master's degree, she would like to take a non-binding course in environmental sciences that is not offered at her university. She discovered the course "Human-Environment Interactions" at the University of Oldenburg through the BIRD Learning Pathfinder and saved it as a favorite. Nadine now wants to register as a guest student and gain access to the course.

Problem definition

Nadine uses [Stud.IP](#), the learning management system (LMS) at her university in Vechta. To attend the "Human-Environment Interactions" course at the University of

Oldenburg, she must enroll as a guest student and use their LMS. She is looking for a way to integrate both LMSs into her personal workspace. Despite being a guest student, Nadine hopes to be able to use both systems easily. However, she doesn't know whether she can connect the LMS platforms to have the courses from both universities in one place.

Background and context

Nadine wants to take a course at another university to determine whether a master's program with a focus on environmental sciences is suitable for her. After choosing the "Human-Environment Interactions" course, she discovers that the University of Oldenburg also uses Stud.IP. This makes it easier for her to participate because she doesn't have to deal with a completely new LMS.

Nadine aims to successfully complete the course to gain further knowledge. She doesn't need any credit points for her current studies, but would still appreciate proof of course attendance.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Nadine wants to make an informed decision about her future educational path and therefore wants to take courses outside of her regular curriculum. Since her university doesn't offer the courses, currently she wants to try to participate in interesting courses at other universities. If this isn't possible due to different LMS or other hurdles, such as registering as a guest student, Nadine would like to limit herself to the offerings at her own university. This could reduce her motivation and make her feel uncertain about choosing her master's program.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Nadine has already tried using online search engines to find information on topics such as "guest auditor status," "taking courses at other universities concurrently," and "using LMS at other universities," but with little success. Each university has different regulations and requirements for registering as a guest student, which makes finding suitable programs complicated. Nadine needs support with the technical requirements of the LMS of her own and other universities.

Activity scenario

Process "Register for a course at another university"

Step 1: Nadine uses the BIRD Learning Pathfinder to find courses at other universities. She enters appropriate search terms and discovers the course "Human-Environment

Interactions" at the University of Oldenburg.

Step 2: Nadine informs herself about the requirements and regulations for becoming a guest auditor at the University of Oldenburg. Then she registers as a guest student on the University of Oldenburg website and receives provisional admission.

Step 3: Nadine receives access information and instructions for registering for the "Human-Environment Interactions" course on Stud.IP at the University of Oldenburg.

Step 4: Nadine enrolls in the course and integrates access to the LMS into her personal workspace at BIRD.

Step 5: Since both University's use Stud.IP, Nadine can use both LMS in her personal workspace.

Step 6: Nadine actively participates in the "Human-Environment Interactions" course and works on her assignments using the connected editors in the workspace.

Step 7: Nadine can create a podcast as part of her exam. She finds the task and the medium very exciting and uploads her finished podcast to the submission folder on Stud.IP for evaluation by the lecturer.

Step 8: After the lecturer has entered the grades into the University of Oldenburg's examination management system, the Office for Guest Auditors creates a module certificate for Nadine, listing the credit points earned and a description of the seminar. Then she transfers this certificate to her data wallet so that she can later submit it to her own university.